

TITLE: AI-BASED DIAGNOSTICS AND A HISTORICAL APPROACH TO IDENTIFYING MISCONCEPTIONS IN THERMODYNAMICS IN MOROCCAN SECONDARY SCHOOLS.

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Abstrat:

Teaching thermodynamics in Moroccan high schools, particularly the concepts of internal and thermal energy, is hindered by persistent conceptual obstacles. This article identifies and analyses five categories of alternative conception documented among first-year mathematics students. To achieve this, we have developed and implemented an AI-powered educational tool based on a large-scale language model (LLM) that can automatically detect alternative conceptions in students' free-response answers and generate personalised, adaptive feedback. An integrated dashboard enables teachers to view the class's conceptual profiles in real time.

Using this tool, we were able to detect several common misconceptions: the representation of heat as a material substance; confusion between heat, temperature and internal energy; an inability to apply the first law of thermodynamics; a language barrier inherent in thermodynamic terminology; and a general resistance to conceptual change. To overcome these obstacles, we propose a two-pronged pedagogical response. First, we suggest a didactic approach based on the history of science, from Lavoisier's caloric theory to Clausius's formulations, to anchor conceptual change in a motivating epistemological trajectory.

The device is subject to empirical validation through a quasi-experimental testing protocol.

Keywords: thermodynamics, alternative conceptions, history of science, artificial intelligence, adaptive feedback, Morocco.